

How to Train a State-of-the-Art Pathology Foundation Model with \$1.6k

Daniel Kaplan, Ratna Sagari Grandhi, Connor Lane, Benjamin Warner, Tanishq Mathew Abraham, Paul S. Scotti

Sophont Technical Report SOPHONT-TR-2025-001. Published November 14, 2025. Version 1.0.

Canonical URL: <https://sophont.med/blog/openmidnight> | Former URL: <https://sophontai.com/blog/openmidnight>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20711012 | Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/20711012>

Code: <https://github.com/MedARC-AI/OpenMidnight> | Model weights: <https://huggingface.co/SophontAI/OpenMidnight> | Demo: <https://huggingface.co/spaces/SophontAI/OpenMidnightDemo>

Abstract We present OpenMidnight, a replication and improvement of the Midnight pathology foundation model, that achieves state-of-the-art performance across multiple benchmarks while being trained on just 12,000 whole-slide images for only \$1.6K. We demonstrate that foundation models for computational pathology do not require massive scale to achieve top performance, and we release the full training pipeline, code, and model weights to accelerate research in this field.

Figure 1: Overview of the OpenMidnight pathology foundation model training and evaluation pipeline.

Introduction

Examining patient tissue under a microscope by a pathologist is an essential step in diagnosing and treating cancer and other diseases. Specifically, a tissue biopsy is taken, and the sample is stained and affixed to a glass slide for the pathologist to analyze. The pathologist performs various tasks, such as detecting abnormal cells and determining the severity of disease. In order to accurately assess the tissue slide, the pathologist has to observe the shape of cells, the organization of cells in the tissue, and more.

Computational pathology (CPath), which is the application of AI to digitized whole-slide images (WSIs), has emerged to augment these workflows. AI systems have been developed for tasks like tumor detection, grading, [1] margin assessment, [2,3] and segmentation. [4] AI can also be used to predict features that doctors otherwise cannot determine from WSIs like survival-risk prediction, [5] drug treatment response, [6,7,8,9] and even inference of certain molecular or gene expression signatures from morphology. [10,11,12,13]

While many early CPath systems were "narrow" deep-learning models trained for a single task (some methods currently approved by the FDA and used in clinical practice), the field is increasingly exploring foundation models. Rather than training a new model for every task, a single pre-trained foundation model can be adapted to many downstream applications in CPath. Companies like Microsoft, [14] Paige, [15] PathAI, [16] Biopimus, [17] and Kaiko.AI [18] have each trained their own foundation models for pathology images. They typically rely on self-supervised learning techniques such as DINOv2 [19] to train transformers to learn meaningful representations using unlabeled data.

The prevailing wisdom is that foundation models should improve with scale, [20] so companies with access to the most data should develop the best performing foundation models. However, this is an assumption worth challenging. In April 2025, Kaiko.AI released a paper titled "Training state-of-the-art pathology foundation models with orders of magnitude less data" in which they presented Midnight, [21] a foundation model trained on just 12,000 whole-slide images (WSIs) from the publicly available TCGA [22] dataset.

Surprisingly, this model performed on par with all the other foundation models, many of which were trained on over a million WSIs!

At Sophont, our initial steps towards training our own pathology foundation model began with a replication of Kaiko.AI's Midnight model, fully open-sourced, including training code and model weights. Through some additional minor pipeline improvements, we achieve state-of-the-art (SOTA) average performance across a variety of benchmarks. We estimate that our model consumed 16x fewer GPU hours and completed in one-quarter of the time it took to train Midnight (single-node 8xH100 for 3.5 days vs. Midnight's 32xH100 for 14 days), costing only \$1.6K USD assuming a cost of \$2.5/H100/hr (exact compute costs may vary).

In this post, we detail how our Midnight replication works and what it means for the field that this model could outperform the competition without scale.

We release this model as OpenMidnight, the first model in our series of pathology foundation models. We open-source the model weights on Hugging Face, and the training code on GitHub. If you're interested in trying out the model, we have a demo.

Results

We evaluate OpenMidnight on a variety of benchmarks supported by eva, an evaluation suite released by Kaiko.ai. These benchmarks cover multiple different downstream proxy tasks, from nucleus segmentation to tumor patch classification to cancer subtyping of WSIs. We also evaluate OpenMidnight on the HEST [13] benchmark, which is a collection of multiple benchmarks for predicting cell gene expression from pathology image patches. Together, these benchmarks expose different strengths and weaknesses of the model being evaluated.

Figure 2: Average performance of top pathology foundation models and baselines. Scores for prior models are taken from Karasikov et al. (2025). [21]

These results show that OpenMidnight's performance is comparable or superior to all other models on all tasks, with our average performance being the highest among the tested models (Figure 2). OpenMidnight achieves a new state-of-the-art on both BreakHis and Cam16(small) scoring 0.946 and 0.873 balanced accuracy, respectively, beating the next best model, UNI-2's 0.860 on BreakHis and 0.873 on Cam16(small).

Note: Note we only compare to open-source models that have already been run on eva by the Kaiko.ai team. We plan to evaluate newer open weights models soon.

Again, it is worth highlighting that OpenMidnight was trained with only 12k slides while UNI-2, the third best model, is trained with over 350k slides!

Table 1a. Classification benchmarks, part 1

Model	#WSIs	PCam (10 shots)	BACH	BRACS	BreakHis	CRC-100K
OpenMidnight (Ours)	12K	0.790	0.916	0.661	0.873	0.961
Midnight	92K	0.900	0.906	0.642	0.850	0.964
UNI-2	350K	0.887	0.914	0.661	0.860	0.965
UNI-2/392	350K	0.821	0.917	0.663	0.829	0.965
Virchow2	3.1M	0.851	0.884	0.624	0.823	0.966
Midnight 92k	92K	0.876	0.896	0.616	0.789	0.966
Midnight 12k	12K	0.791	0.904	0.644	0.841	0.966
H-Optimus-0	500K	0.824	0.757	0.615	0.808	0.956
Kaiko-B8	29K	0.786	0.872	0.617	0.825	0.957
TCGA-100M	12K	0.774	0.864	0.615	0.779	0.967
Prov-GigaPath	171K	0.852	0.766	0.616	0.821	0.951
Hibou-L	1.1M	0.804	0.811	0.637	0.740	0.933
UNI	100K	0.815	0.791	0.593	0.789	0.948
UNI/512	100K	0.737	0.877	0.612	0.732	0.950
Phikon	12K	0.820	0.735	0.568	0.713	0.942
Phikon v2	60K	0.741	0.734	0.600	0.716	0.939
DINOV2-giant (pretrained)	0	0.719	0.725	0.583	0.832	0.935
DINOV2-giant (random)	0	0.649	0.473	0.411	0.427	0.748

Table 1b. Classification benchmarks, part 2

Model	#WSIs	Gleason	MHIST	PCam	Cam16 (small)	Panda (small)
OpenMidnight (Ours)	12K	0.817	0.844	0.938	0.946	0.652
Midnight	92K	0.809	0.825	0.951	0.831	0.633
UNI-2	350K	0.778	0.823	0.949	0.868	0.659
UNI-2/392	350K	0.791	0.849	0.927	0.858	0.653
Virchow2	3.1M	0.778	0.861	0.936	0.865	0.656
Midnight 92k	92K	0.820	0.811	0.950	0.861	0.625
Midnight 12k	12K	0.801	0.807	0.930	0.850	0.663
H-Optimus-0	500K	0.771	0.842	0.942	0.838	0.670
Kaiko-B8	29K	0.748	0.828	0.917	0.831	0.642
TCGA-100M	12K	0.799	0.792	0.927	0.852	0.667
Prov-GigaPath	171K	0.720	0.831	0.942	0.791	0.660
Hibou-L	1.1M	0.763	0.839	0.952	0.823	0.634
UNI	100K	0.757	0.840	0.938	0.822	0.655
UNI/512	100K	0.754	0.814	0.883	0.814	0.654
Phikon	12K	0.729	0.804	0.923	0.809	0.644
Phikon v2	60K	0.755	0.784	0.893	0.803	0.631
DINOV2-giant (pretrained)	0	0.744	0.862	0.874	0.507	0.382
DINOV2-giant (random)	0	0.464	0.569	0.755	0.566	0.308

Table 1c. Segmentation, regression, and average performance

Model	#WSIs	CoNSeP	MoNuSAC	HEST	Average
OpenMidnight (Ours)	12K	0.631	0.655	0.390	0.775
Midnight	92K	0.663	0.707	0.384	0.774
UNI-2	350K	0.628	0.644	0.414	0.773
UNI-2/392	350K	0.629	0.659	0.407	0.767
Virchow2	3.1M	0.639	0.676	0.398	0.766
Midnight 92k	92K	0.629	0.656	0.392	0.761
Midnight 12k	12K	0.626	0.663	0.395	0.760
H-Optimus-0	500K	0.644	0.685	0.415	0.751
Kaiko-B8	29K	0.643	0.686	0.373	0.748
TCGA-100M	12K	0.622	0.656	0.396	0.747
Prov-GigaPath	171K	0.626	0.687	0.393	0.743
Hibou-L	1.1M	0.645	0.668	0.388	0.740
UNI	100K	0.627	0.659	0.386	0.740
UNI/512	100K	0.621	0.658	0.364	0.728
Phikon	12K	0.623	0.644	0.367	0.717
Phikon v2	60K	0.626	0.645	0.375	0.711
DINOv2-giant (pretrained)	0	0.564	0.614	0.342	0.668
DINOv2-giant (random)	0	0.461	0.428	0.172	0.495

Performance comparison of OpenMidnight to existing pathology foundation models on eva+HEST benchmarks. Scores for existing models are taken from Karasikov et al. (2025). [21] We report balanced accuracy for the classification tasks, Dice score for semantic segmentation (CoNSeP and MoNuSAC), and the average Pearson correlation for the nine HEST regression tasks. Only performance with [CLS] token is reported. Best score per dataset is bolded.

Note: We currently evaluate linear probes only with [CLS] tokens instead of [CLS]+mean tokens. We plan to run [CLS]+mean token evaluations soon.

We also qualitatively evaluated the representations learned by OpenMidnight. We took images from the BACH dataset of breast cancer images, passed them through our model, and visualized the embeddings produced by our model using t-SNE (Figure 3). We see a clear separation between different classes and also observe sensible organization of images in the t-SNE space: normal images are closer to benign images than invasive carcinoma images. We also compare these representations to those of a pretrained DINOv2 ViT-G, which lacks any clear separation between classes.

Figure 3: t-SNE of CLS token embeddings of images from the BACH dataset from both DINOv2 ViT-G and OpenMidnight. The embeddings from the OpenMidnight foundation model show clear separation across classes, as opposed to the embeddings from the DINOv2 ViT G model.

In addition, we perform a principal component feature analysis within single images of the MoNuSAC [23] dataset (Figure 4). Here we see the principal components picking up on different structures within the image.

Figure 4: PCA analysis of MoNuSAC embeddings. It's possible to visualize different tissue components using PCA.

How we did it

Our training approach does not differ significantly from other SOTA pathology foundation models, which utilize Meta's DINOv2. However, we mostly follow the original Midnight paper, [21] which makes a few changes that likely enable more data-efficient training.

We start with a pretrained 1.1B parameter ViT-G DINOv2 [19]. We suspect that initialization with the pretrained checkpoint enables faster convergence and more efficient training. We also use the KDE regularizer [24] to help with stable training, replacing KoLeo [25] typically used in DINOv2.

Note: Note that many previous pathology foundation models train a DINOv2 on pathology data completely from scratch.

OpenMidnight also utilizes augmentations in the Hematoxylin-Eosin-DAB colorspace to increase the diversity of the training data and improve robustness of the model. We also applied these augmentations, but we qualitatively observed that the initial augmentations applied to the image patches during DINOv2 were quite strong, so we decreased the strength of these augmentations.

A majority of the prior works divide up the large whole-slide images into non-overlapping patches of size 224/256 ahead of time, and save them offline. OpenMidnight switched to an online patching approach, where the patches are sampled from the whole-slide image during training. We differ from OpenMidnight by utilizing a variation of offline patching, in which we instead precompute the image patches. However, we still select the patches randomly from within the image, allowing for overlaps. We also perform filtering of non-informative patches like in OpenMidnight. [21,15]

We train OpenMidnight only on one publicly available dataset: TCGA, [22] which contains 12K Formalin-Fixed, Paraffin-Embedded (FFPE) slides from 32 different cancer types. Note that while some pathology foundation models also train on this dataset, most utilize large-scale proprietary datasets.

Note: We only train on images from tissue slides stained with H&E, which is the primary staining used in pathology. In future work, we hope to expand to other stain types and IHC.

We train using 8 Nvidia-H100 GPUs (80GB memory) at a batch size of 48 per GPU (384 total batch size), for 250K steps, at a learning rate of $2.0e-4$ with the AdamW [26] optimizer. This takes around 83.33 wall-clock hours (667 GPU hours), with 96M image patches seen, and 29M unique image patches.

Note: Note the original Midnight paper used a learning rate of $3.5e-4$.

The current state of pathology foundation models

The surprising performance of OpenMidnight motivates us to take a closer look at the state of pathology foundation models.

All the top CPath foundation models were trained nearly identically, with the biggest difference coming from the private data sources used to train the model. Everyone seems to follow the same recipe of DINOv2 from scratch on patches of whole-slide images, with a few groups identifying benefits from things like swapping out KoLeo [25] with KDE [24] regularization, discarding patches that contain primarily adipose tissue, and performing data augmentation steps curated better for pathology slides than natural images.

Despite almost identical model architectures, downstream performance across the foundation model landscape is messy. Among the top models, there isn't a clear winner in performance across all the benchmarks (see table above). Additionally, Figure 5 (numbers pulled from prior works) demonstrates that when training pathology foundation models, average performance is not cleanly correlated with the compute used or dataset size.

Note: This aligns with what Campanella et al. (2025) [27] observed when benchmarking foundation models on a suite of clinical datasets.

Figure 5: Average model performance plotted against amount of training compute and dataset size. Compute is normalized to H100 GPU-hours. Models that do not report training compute or dataset size are omitted. Poor scaling of pathology foundation models is observed.

These observations reveal some of the limitations of the current state of the field. We come to two conclusions. First, OpenMidnight demonstrates that we can push foundation models on limited data much further than previously thought. Second, the messy performance landscape points to a broader concern: whether these benchmarks are truly reflective of real-world use-cases. Perhaps performance completely changes when applied to more sophisticated downstream use-cases beyond linear probes on basic classification tasks. Additionally, we note that datasets used for benchmarking are often low-quality or are improperly preprocessed during benchmark evaluation. For instance, we observed that vision transformers pretrained only on ImageNet (i.e., a model that has never seen a pathology slide) can actually outperform all pathology foundation models on the MHIST dataset. [28] For these reasons, we urge the field to adopt better-curated benchmarks, rigorous preprocessing checks, and develop more practically oriented standardized evaluations; frameworks like eva were a much-needed step towards reproducible comparisons but further work is needed to align evaluations with clinical utility. Unfortunately, the most clinically relevant datasets and benchmarks are private, and we encourage the community to open-source better real-world benchmarks.

Open-sourcing the full pipeline

We believe that fully open-sourcing the code, weights, and evaluation scripts lowers the barrier to entry, and accelerates progress in CPath with improved trust and reproducibility.

We hope that OpenMidnight will serve as an accessible baseline for pathology foundation models, and our open-source training pipeline will expand participation in the development of the next generation of pathology foundation models. Students, clinicians, and researchers without access to large compute clusters or private datasets can work together with us on methods to improve the field for everyone.

We request the CPath community to experiment with OpenMidnight and test out the model in their own research, and share any interesting results with us in the MedARC community Discord server here.

We are also building in public and welcome collaborators of all forms in the MedARC Discord server as we develop our next model, one that will deviate further from prevailing recipes to hopefully deliver larger practical gains (including better whole-slide context and a DINOv3 backbone).

Additionally, we are hiring a founding pathology foundation models research lead. If this is your area, see the full role here.

Finally, if you are a life sciences company/startup, hospital, clinician, etc. interested in applying our models to your own use cases, contact us [here](#).

Acknowledgments

We thank Mikhail Karasikov for answering questions about Midnight. We thank Nicolas Kanzig for answering questions about eva. We thank the members of MedARC and the broader research community for their feedback and support. We are very grateful to FAL AI for granting compute to support this open-source research.

Citation

For attribution in academic contexts, please cite this work as

Daniel Kaplan, Ratna Sagari Grandhi, Connor Lane, Benjamin Warner, Tanishq Mathew Abraham, and Paul S. Scotti. How to Train a State-of-the-Art Pathology Foundation Model with \$1.6k. Sophont Technical Report SOPHONT-TR-2025-001, 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.20711012. <https://sophont.med/blog/openmidnight>.

BibTeX citation

```
@techreport{kaplan2025openmidnight,  
  author = {Kaplan, Daniel and Grandhi, Ratna Sagari and Lane, Connor and Warner, Benjamin and Abraham, Tanishq Mathew and Scotti, Paul S.},  
  title = {How to Train a State-of-the-Art Pathology Foundation Model with \$.6k},  
  institution = {Sophont},  
  number = {SOPHONT-TR-2025-001},  
  year = {2025},  
  doi = {10.5281/zenodo.20711012},  
  url = {https://sophont.med/blog/openmidnight},  
}
```

References

- [0] Kaplan, Daniel, Grandhi, Ratna Sagari, Lane, Connor, Warner, Benjamin, Abraham, Tanishq Mathew, and Scotti, Paul S. How to Train a State-of-the-Art Pathology Foundation Model with \$1.6k. Sophont Technical Report SOPHONT-TR-2025-001, 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.20711012. <https://sophont.med/blog/openmidnight>.
- [1] Lu, Ming Y, Williamson, Drew FK, Chen, Tiffany Y, Chen, Richard J, Barbieri, Matteo, Mahmood, Faisal. Data-efficient and weakly supervised computational pathology on whole-slide images. *Nature biomedical engineering*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 555-570, 2021.
- [2] Hollon, Todd C, Pandian, Balaji, Adapa, Arjun R, Urias, Esteban, Save, Akshay V, Khalsa, Siri Sahib S, Eichberg, Daniel G, D'Amico, Randy S, et al.. Near real-time intraoperative brain tumor diagnosis using stimulated Raman histology and deep neural networks. *Nature medicine*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 52-58, 2020.
- [3] Campanella, Gabriele, Nehal, Kishwer S, Lee, Erica H, Rossi, Anthony, Possum, Brandon, Manuel, Genna, Fuchs, Thomas J, Busam, Klaus J. A deep learning algorithm with high sensitivity for the detection of basal cell carcinoma in Mohs micrographic surgery frozen sections. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, vol. 85, no. 5, pp. 1285-1286, 2021.
- [4] Graham, Simon, Vu, Quoc Dang, Raza, Shan E Ahmed, Azam, Ayesha, Tsang, Yee Wah, Kwak, Jin Tae, Rajpoot, Nasir. Hover-net: Simultaneous segmentation and classification of nuclei in multi-tissue histology images. *Medical image analysis*, vol. 58, pp. 101563, 2019.
- [5] Kather, Jakob Nikolas, Krisam, Johannes, Charoentong, Pornpimol, Luedde, Tom, Herpel, Esther, Weis, Cleo-Aron, Gaiser, Timo, Marx, Alexander, et al.. Predicting survival from colorectal cancer histology slides using deep learning: A retrospective multicenter study. *PLoS medicine*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. e1002730, 2019.
- [6] Ahn, Byungsoo, Moon, Damin, Kim, Hyun-Soo, Lee, Chung, Cho, Nam Hoon, Choi, Heung-Kook, Kim, Dongmin, Lee, Jung-Yun, et al.. Histopathologic image-based deep learning classifier for predicting platinum-based treatment responses in high-grade serous ovarian cancer. *Nature communications*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 4253, 2024.
- [7] Vanguri, Rami S, Luo, Jia, Aukerman, Andrew T, Egger, Jacklynn V, Fong, Christopher J, Horvat, Nataly, Pagano, Andrew, Araujo-Filho, Jose de Arimateia Batista, et al.. Multimodal integration of radiology, pathology and genomics for prediction of response to PD-(L) 1 blockade in patients with non-small cell lung cancer. *Nature cancer*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 1151-1164, 2022.
- [8] Jasti, Jay, Zhong, Hua, Panwar, Vandana, Jarmale, Vipul, Miyata, Jeffrey, Carrillo, Deyssy, Christie, Alana, Rakheja, Dinesh, et al.. Histopathology based AI model predicts anti-angiogenic therapy response in renal cancer clinical trial. *Nature communications*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 2610, 2025.
- [9] Hoang, Danh-Tai, Dinstag, Gal, Shulman, Eldad D, Hermida, Leandro C, Ben-Zvi, Doreen S, Elis, Efrat, Caley, Katherine, Sammut, Stephen-John, et al.. A deep-learning framework to predict cancer treatment response from histopathology images through imputed transcriptomics. *Nature cancer*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 1305-1317, 2024.
- [10] Kather, Jakob Nikolas, Heij, Lara R, Grabsch, Heike I, Loeffler, Chiara, Echle, Amelie, Muti, Hannah Sophie, Krause, Jeremias, Niehues, Jan M, et al.. Pan-cancer image-based detection of clinically actionable genetic alterations. *Nature cancer*, vol. 1, no. 8, pp. 789-799, 2020.
- [11] Coudray, Nicolas, Ocampo, Paolo Santiago, Sakellaropoulos, Theodore, Narula, Navneet, Snuderl, Matija, Fenyo, David, Moreira, Andre L, Razavian, Narges, et al.. Classification and mutation prediction from non-small cell lung cancer histopathology images using deep learning. *Nature medicine*, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. 1559-1567, 2018.
- [12] Kather, Jakob Nikolas, Pearson, Alexander T, Halama, Niels, Jager, Dirk, Krause, Jeremias, Loosen, Sven H, Marx, Alexander, Boor, Peter, et al.. Deep learning can predict microsatellite instability directly from histology in gastrointestinal cancer. *Nature medicine*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 1054-1056, 2019.
- [13] Guillaume Jaume, Paul Doucet, Andrew H. Song, Ming Y. Lu, Cristina Almagro-Perez, Sophia J. Wagner, Anurag J. Vaidya, Richard J. Chen, et al.. HEST-1k: A Dataset for Spatial Transcriptomics and Histology Image Analysis. arXiv, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.16192>.
- [14] Xu, Hanwen, Usuyama, Naoto, Bagga, Jaspreet, Zhang, Sheng, Rao, Rajesh, Naumann, Tristan, Wong, Cliff, Gero, Zelalem, et al.. A whole-slide foundation model for digital pathology from real-world data. *Nature*, vol. 630, no. 8015, pp. 181-188, 2024.
- [15] Zimmermann, Eric, Vorontsov, Eugene, Viret, Julian, Casson, Adam, Zelechowski, Michal, Shaikovski, George, Tenenholtz, Neil, Hall, James, et al.. Virchow2: Scaling self-supervised mixed magnification models in pathology. arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.00738, 2024.
- [16] Dinkar Juyal, Harshith Padigela, Chintan Shah, Daniel Shenker, Natalia Harguindeguy, Yi Liu, Blake Martin, Yibo Zhang, et al.. PLUTO: Pathology-Universal Transformer. arXiv, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.07905>.
- [17] Saillard, Charlie, Jenatton, Rodolphe, Llinares-Lopez, Felipe, Mariet, Zeld, Cahane, David, Durand, Eric, Vert, Jean-Philippe. H-optimus-0. 2024. <https://github.com/bioptimus/releases/tree/main/models/h-optimus/v0>.
- [18] kaiko.ai, Nanne Aben, Edwin D. de Jong, Ioannis Gatopoulos, Nicolas Kanzig, Mikhail Karasikov, Axel Lagre, Roman Moser, et al.. Towards Large-Scale Training of Pathology Foundation Models. arXiv, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.15217>.
- [19] Maxime Oquab, Timothee Darcet, Theo Moutakanni, Huy Vo, Marc Szafranec, Vasil Khalidov, Pierre Fernandez, Daniel Haziza, et al.. DINOv2: Learning Robust Visual Features without Supervision. arXiv, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07193>.
- [20] Jared Kaplan, Sam McCandlish, Tom Henighan, Tom B. Brown, Benjamin Chess, Rewon Child, Scott Gray, Alec Radford, et al.. Scaling Laws for Neural Language Models. arXiv, 2020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.08361>.
- [21] Mikhail Karasikov, Joost van Doorn, Nicolas Kanzig, Melis Erdal Cesur, Hugo Mark Horlings, Robert Berke, Fei Tang, Sebastian Otolara. Training state-of-the-art pathology foundation models with orders of magnitude less data. arXiv, 2025. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.05186>.
- [22] Weinstein, John N, Collisson, Eric A, Mills, Gordon B, Shaw, Kenna R Mills, Ozenberger, Brad A, Ellrott, Kyle, Shmulevich, Ilya, Sander, Chris, et al.. The Cancer Genome Atlas Pan-Cancer analysis project. *Nat Genet*, vol. 45, no. 10, pp. 1113-1120, 2013. doi:10.1038/ng.2764.
- [23] Verma, Ruchika, Kumar, Neeraj, Patil, Abhijeet, Kurian, Nikhil Cherian, Rane, Swapnil, Graham, Simon, Vu, Quoc Dang, Zwager, Mieke, et al.. MoNuSAC2020: A multi-organ nuclei segmentation and classification challenge. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 40, no. 12, pp. 3413-3423, 2021.
- [24] Wang, Tongzhou, Isola, Phillip. Understanding contrastive representation learning through alignment and uniformity on the hypersphere. *International conference on machine learning*, pp. 9929-9939, 2020.
- [25] Sablayrolles, Alexandre, Douze, Matthijs, Schmid, Cordelia, Jegou, Herve. Spreading vectors for similarity search. arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.03198, 2018.
- [26] Loshchilov, Ilya, Hutter, Frank. Decoupled weight decay regularization. arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.05101, 2017.
- [27] Campanella, Gabriele, Chen, Shengjia, Singh, Manbir, Verma, Ruchika, Muehlstedt, Silke, Zeng, Jennifer, Stock, Aryeh, Croken, Matt, et al.. A clinical benchmark of public self-supervised pathology foundation models. *Nature Communications*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 3640, 2025.
- [28] Ignatov, Andrey, Malivenko, Grigory. NCT-CRC-HE: Not All Histopathological Datasets are Equally Useful. *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 300-317, 2024.